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STRENGTHENING THE TECHNICAL COMPETENCIES OF EDUCATION PROFESSORS AMONG TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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The study assessed the technical competencies among faculty members within Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) with the purpose of proposing a technical report towards academic excellence. Specifically, it described the profile of the respondents, determined the extent of manifestation of competencies in instruction, research, and extension. Further, the study ascertained the initiatives toward successful academic offering which contributed to the proposed technical report as input to TEIs' academic excellence.

The study utilized a descriptive type of research with 199 college professors in the selected TEIs in the province. The study made use of questionnaire, interview and focused group discussion as the data gathering instruments. The study is limited to the responses of the target respondents. Weighted mean, and composite mean are the statistical treatment used.

Based on the findings, majority of the professors are within the age range of 30 to 39 years old, predominantly female, with relevant Master's degree, and are Assistant and Associate Professors, had been in the service for 6 to 10 years. Moreover, they manifest technical competencies in instruction, research and extension to a moderate extent. Meanwhile, the study identified promoting a safe and positive environment in which student are responsible self-motivated and self-evaluating, and fulfilling the career of the college students to master a specific industry specialization as the initiatives to successful academic offering. The proposed technical report is substantial to the enhancement in terms of professors' performance.

Keywords: *Technical Competencies, TEIs, Instruction, Research, Extension*

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